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Attitude towards Blended Teaching-Learning Approach: A Study on Postgraduate Students

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Abstract: This study examined attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach among post-graduate students. The descriptive survey method was used with self-created questionnaire (ATBTLA) to examine attitude of postgraduate students, (N=313) toward the blended teaching-learning approach. For data analysis, the investigators developed a research model using SPSS-23 and graphical representation to represent the attitude towards the blended teaching-learning approach. The present study revealed that most students (68.89%) scored between 56.03 and 66.01, indicating a moderate attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach. It was also found that most students were satisfied with the blended teaching-learning process. The results revealed that there was no difference in the PG level students' attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach based on gender (0.101, $p>0.05$), residence (0.568, $p>0.05$), family type (1.058, $p>0.05$), semester at university (1.302, $p>0.05$), nature of course (1.531, $p>0.05$), nature of internet access (0.343, $p>0.05$), devices used for learning (0.043, $p>0.05$), their experience of using the blended mode of learning (0.813, $p>0.05$) towards the blended teaching-learning approach. The findings suggest that students believed that providing the course in a blended style made it easier to follow and boosted their learning.

Keywords: Blended learning, teaching-learning, attitude, satisfaction, post graduate students.

Introduction

The Commonwealth of Learning (COL) defines blended learning “as when the same students enrolled in the same course use both online and conventional classroom instruction to study the same material” (*Blended Learning – Guide to Blended Learning*, n.d.). Blended learning has been a popular teaching and learning strategy in recent years, with several educational institutions worldwide adopting it (Wani & Dalvi, 2013). Blended learning is seen as alternative teaching and learning strategy

that enables teachers to solve a fundamental problem in online interaction which is the need for more familiarity with conventional face-to-face interactions between students and teachers (Kuo et al., 2014). It is a form of teaching that uses online communication tools, web-based content, and a learning management system to enable teachers to balance the amount of in-class and computer-internet-based learning (Mulyono et al., 2007). Students gain from this balance because they can access dependable learning materials and may study quickly, communicate with teachers, and track their progress. One of the possible advantages of the blended learning strategy is that it reduces the gap between face-to-face and online classes (Kuo et al., 2014). It might be any learning program in which multiple delivery modalities are employed to enhance educational results and reduce program delivery costs.

Blended learning refers to a kind of education that combines face-to-face and online delivery techniques (Chew et al., 2010). Since it mixes the conventional classroom method with the online learning paradigm, blended learning is appealing and practical (Yilmaz & Malone, 2020). Blended learning's mode of delivery provides learners with an efficient and effective educational experience, with the added benefit of increased learner accessibility to programs; thus, the blended model can be used in novel ways to improve both student learning outcomes and instructional delivery costs (Dziuban et al., 2004). Students' communication skills increase due to blended learning, which allows for student-teacher exchanges and accelerates student-teacher involvement in both traditional and online environments (Kumar et al., 2017). Students can speak with their professors and classmates beyond class, giving teachers and students the freedom to organize their learning, monitor their progress anytime they were, and be conscious of their learning (Das & Barman, 2023).

Learners and lecturers should be physically present in a blended learning setting. Despite this, students should be able to utilize digital tools to exert some control over the pace or themes of their learning (Devi et al., 2021). A comparable approach is the flipped learning model, which uses technology to rearrange the learning experience and maximize crucial face-to-face interaction in the classroom. In a flipped classroom, students would be encouraged to use a cloud-based learning platform to access digital learning resources on their own time. Before each lesson, resources such as video lectures, podcasts, recordings, and articles would be offered to transfer most of the essential information from teacher to student. This saves class time for educators to assist students in activities, conduct discussions, and encourage student participation (Das & Barman, 2023). This paper aims at highlighting the attitude of post graduate students towards the blended teaching-learning approach.

Review of related literature

The study by Korkmaz and Karakus (2009) revealed that blended learning models had a greater impact on students' attitudes toward geography classes than traditional

learning models, as well as a positive relationship between students' attitudes toward geography classes and their rational thinking levels. Another research by Johnson (2013) indicated significant differences in the overall opinions of the student groups about blended and online learning. Acar (2013) found that attitudes regarding using social media for academic purposes were not connected to using other kinds of online learning techniques or getting experience with a Facebook-type page. Wani and Dalvi (2013) discovered that exposing foundation year students to blended learning activities positively impacted their engagement, contentment with the teacher's role, and test performance while studying English. In a study on perceptions and attitudes toward blended learning, Hassan (2015) found that students were satisfied with the method because it improved their English language proficiency and made learning English more cooperative, engaging, and enjoyable. A different investigation by AlAbdulkarim and Albarrak (2015) indicated that students valued collaborative learning more than any other. The findings showed that students had a favourable attitude and were very motivated about the blended approach of teaching research courses.

According to Angadi (2016), there were no significant differences in B.Ed. student-teachers' perceptions of blended learning based on their gender or academic level. Most prospective teachers had a positive attitude toward blended learning, and prospective female teachers are substantially more so than their male colleagues (Khan, 2016). Obaidat (2016) found that teachers' attitudes regarding implementing blended learning in the elementary stage were highly statistically significant (3.79). Lalima and Dangwal, (2017) suggested that blended learning implementation is effective and requires diligent efforts, the appropriate mentality, sizable funding, and strongly motivated instructors and learners. Alzahrani and Toole (2017) revealed that pupils have both experiences utilizing the internet and a favourable opinion about it. Interesting exchanges surrounding the student study year included positive and negative responses to Internet use and a preference for integrated learning. According to the findings of another research by Birbal et al. (2018), instructors believed that technology and learning flexibility were the most significant or valued aspects of blended learning. Additionally, there were notable differences in the students' opinions depending on their gender and part-time or full-time employment level.

Akbarov et al. (2018) research demonstrated that students like blended learning in EFL use over conventional classroom instruction, and there is also a positive correlation between these preferences. Bakeer (2018) discovered that students' opinions about incorporating blended learning seemed to have a favourable impact on improving their language abilities, independent development, and learner engagement. The studies of Aladwan et al. (2018) showed that blended learning benefits learners and that most participants completely comprehend the objectives of e-learning when they participate in blended learning. Nortvig et al. (2018) revealed numerous aspects such as educator involvement in virtual interactions

and interactions between students, instructors, and material. They intended links between offline and online and between campus-related and training activities. Blended learning is more suitable than conventional learning (Ikhwan & Widodo, 2019). Another study by Karaaslan and Kılıç, (2019) revealed that top achievers tended to favour blended learning. Students demonstrated strong preferences for the perception and notions of blended learning, according to Vaksalla et al. (2019). The usefulness of using evolving ICT tools, strategies, and approaches as a new, inventive kind of online instruction and learning platform was discovered by Dahal et al., (2020).

Rahman et al., (2020) conducted a study and discovered that blended learning via the i-Learn platform provides excellent flexibility, allowing students to learn anytime and anywhere. Saboowala and Mishra, (2020) indicating that blended learning for school teachers' professional development after the pandemic would push the frontiers of learning by fostering international cooperation between diverse educational societies. This study relied on the interactive impact of the highest education level of the educator and the instructors who have applied education and instruction via online line sessions. Abbacan-Tuguic, (2021) identified technological weaknesses, which include the absence of educational devices and erratic internet access, which limit the effective application of blended learning adaptation. In another study Jnr (2022) demonstrated that social variables, including usage, difficulty, work satisfaction, lengthy effects, enabling circumstances, and IT experience greatly impact lecturers' perceptions of adopting BL efforts to enhance educational tasks in higher education. Falah and Chairuddin (2022) revealed that 76.3% of students responded that they were happy with the integration of blended learning, indicating that a favourable view from the students.

Considering all of these factors, the researchers felt that there is a gap in which more research must be conducted to study in-depth outcomes about the attitude towards the blended teaching-learning approach. Therefore, the researchers chose this particular area for their study.

Research Questions

RQ₁, What is the level of attitude of postgraduate students towards blended teaching-learning?

RQ₂, What is the level of satisfaction of postgraduate level students towards blended teaching-learning?

RQ₃, How is the attitude differing towards blended teaching-learning based on gender, residence, family type, semester etc.?

Research Objectives

The researcher framed the following objectives to carry out the study:

O₁ To study the level of attitude of Post Graduate students towards the blended mode of teaching and learning.

O₂ To study the level of satisfaction of Post Graduate students towards the blended mode of teaching and learning.

O₃ To find out the mean difference of their attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on gender, residence, family type, semester, nature of the course, nature of internet access, their experience of using the blended mode to get learning, and the devices used for learning.

Hypotheses of the study

H₀₁: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on gender.

H₀₂: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on residence.

H₀₃: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on the family type.

H₀₄: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on semester.

H₀₅: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on the nature of course.

H₀₆: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on the nature of internet access.

H₀₇: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on their experience of using the blended mode to get learning.

H₀₈: There exist no significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on the devices used for learning.

Methods

Research methodology

For this investigation, the researchers employed a descriptive survey method. Therefore, the investigators gathered and analysed data that is quantitative.

Population and Sample

For the purposes of this study, the population was all West Bengal University students enrolled in PG programs for the current academic year in the Uttar Dinajpur district.

In the current study, only 313 students from various Postgraduate departments of Raiganj University in the Uttar Dinajpur area made up the sample for this study. The technique of random sampling was employed for selecting the sample. The researchers initially chose a variety of higher education institutions in the district of Uttar Dinajpur. Then, in order to get accurate, genuine, and unbiased data, the researchers randomly selected 103 students from higher education institutions.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample

SL No.	Name of the University	Department	Total Number of Sample	Boys	Girls
1.	Raiganj University	Language	49	20	29
		Science	218	105	113
		Social Science	46	31	15
Total			313	156	157

Table 1 depicts the representation of examined samples representing Post Graduate students (under current study) from the Raiganj University of the Uttar Dinajpur district in West Bengal, India.

Tool used

To fulfil the objectives, the investigators developed a scale on ‘Attitude Towards the Blended Teaching-Learning Approach’ of the Postgraduate level students (ATBTLA). The ATBTLA of the postgraduate students was assessed based on a 3-point Likert scale from 1 to 3, similar to the previous investigations conducted and used by Hassan (2015), Obaidat (2016), Yulia (2017), Aladwan et al., (2018), Bakeer (2018), Abbacan-Tuguic (2021) Fenech et al., (2021), Falah and Chairuddin, (2022) Nyaaba and Sandawey (2022). The questionnaire was constructed with 30 items which were distributed into eight dimensions, i.e., teaching-learning process (3 items), learning activities (4 items), psychological aspects (5 items), curriculum (3 items), technological facilities (5 items), efficiency of teacher (4 items), performance of the learners (3 items), evaluation process (3 items).

Data collection procedure

In order to begin gathering data, the Raiganj University was chosen randomly in the district of Uttar Dinajpur, West Bengal. Following that, the investigators notified the authorities and the pertinent PG students of each department well in advance for the purpose of data gathering. The researchers created online questionnaire using Google Forms, and the questionnaire was distributed via WhatsApp, email, and other social media platforms. Before and throughout the data-collecting procedure, the students received clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaires. In the end, 313 completed responses were gathered. However, 10 responses were turned down due to specific issues with incompleteness. After gathering and sorting

the surveys, the investigators evaluated all of the questionnaire items using the direct and reverse scoring methods. Positive items were scored using the direct technique (Agree-3, Neutral-2, Disagree-1), while negative items were scored using the reverse method (Agree-1, Neutral-2, Disagree-3).

Statistical techniques used

The present study was a survey-based descriptive study. The researchers had randomly selected only 313 students from different departments of post-graduate level students of Raiganj University Uttar Dinajpur district, W.B., as sample. The investigator extensively used SPSS 23 to analyse the Mean, S.D, t-test, and ANOVA.

Results and Findings

A) Level of attitude of the postgraduate students towards the blended teaching-learning approach

Table 2: Mean, SD of the level of attitude scale

Group	Number	Mean	S.D
Post Graduate students	313	61.029	4.9906

For determining the level of attitude

$$M \pm \sigma$$

$$M + \sigma = 61.029 + 4.9906 = 66.019$$

$$M - \sigma = 61.029 - 4.9906 = 56.038$$

Table 3: Level of attitude among the Post Graduate students towards the blended teaching-learning approach

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Attitude Towards Blended Teaching-Learning
≥ 66.019	50	15.97%	High
Between 56.038 to 66.019	215	68.89%	Moderate
≤ 56.038	48	15.33%	Low
Total	313	100%	

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

Based on the Table no.2 and 3, it was observed that out of the total 313 students, 50 (15.97%) of students scored above 66.019, 215 (68.89%) students scored between 56.038 to 66.019, and 48 (15.33%) students scored

below 56.038 on the attitude scale towards blended teaching-learning. Therefore, the majority of students (68.89%) scored between 56.038 and 66.019, indicating a moderate attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach among post-graduate level students (Mahato et al., 2021).

B) Level of satisfaction of the Post Graduate students towards the blended teaching-learning approach

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the level of satisfaction to learn through blended teaching-learning approach

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

Figure 1 shows that out of 313 students, 231(73.80%) students responded with ‘yes’ regarding their level of satisfaction with blended teaching-learning. On the other hand, 83 (26.51) students responded ‘no.’ So, most of the students were satisfied with the blended teaching-learning approach.

C) Mean differences of their attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach

Table 4: Number, Mean, SD and t-test regarding different demographic variables

Demographic Variables	Number (N)	Mean (M)	SD (σ)	df	Mean Difference	S _{ED}	t-value	Sig. (2-tail)	Re-marks*
Gender	Male	156	61.00	4.81	311	.0573	.565	0.101	.919
	Female	157	61.05	5.17					
Residence	Rural	184	61.16	5.40	311	.3258	.573	0.568	.570
	Urban	129	60.83	4.34					
Family Type	Nuclear	228	60.84	5.25	311	.6712	.634	1.058	.291
	Joint	85	61.51	4.17					
Semester at University	1 st sem	153	60.65	5.29	311	.6712	.563	1.302	.194
	3 rd sem	160	61.38	4.66					

Access to the Internet at home	Yes	293	61.00	5.06	311	.3966	1.155	0.343	.732	(p>0.05)*
	No	20	61.40	3.84						
Their experience of using the blended mode to get learning	Yes	253	60.91	5.12	311	.5830	.717	0.813	.417	(p>0.05)*
	No	60	61.50	4.38						

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

Gender and Attitude towards BL

Table 4 shows that the determined 't'-value is 0.101, less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 311 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be said that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of male and female students toward the blended teaching-learning approach.

Residence and Attitude towards BL

Table 4 shows that the determined 't'-value is 0.568, less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 311 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be said that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of rural and urban students toward the blended teaching-learning approach.

Semester and Attitude towards BL

Table 4 shows that the determined 't'-value is 1.302, which is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 311 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be said that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of the 1st semester and 3rd semester students towards the teaching-learning approach.

Access to the Internet and Attitude towards BL

Table 4 shows that the determined 't'-value is 0.343, which is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 311 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be said that there is no significant difference in the attitudes towards the teaching-learning approach based on access to the internet at home.

Experience of using BL and attitude towards BL

Table 4 shows that the determined 't'-value is 0.813, which is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 311 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null

hypothesis is accepted and it can be said that there is no significant difference in the attitudes towards teaching-learning based on their experience of using the blended mode to get learning.

Table 5: Number, Mean and SD in attitude towards teaching-learning approach based on the nature of course and devices used for learning

Variables		Number (N)	Mean (M)	SD (σ)
Nature of Course	Language	49	61.347	5.1298
	Science	218	61.206	5.0599
	Social Science	46	59.848	4.4119
Devices used for learning	By using Smartphone	193	60.974	5.4548
	By using Laptop/Desktop	75	61.173	4.2215
	By using Tab/Notepad	45	61.022	4.0926

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

Table 6: The significant mean differences regarding attitude towards blended teaching-learning based on the nature of course and devices used for learning

Result of ANOVA based on Nature of Course					
Sum of Squares		Mean Square		F-value	Sig.
Between Groups	Within Groups	Between Groups	Within Groups		
75.993	7694.748	37.997	.218	1.531@	.218
Result of ANOVA based on Devices used for learning					
2.146	7768.595	1.073	25.060	.043@	.958

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

@ Not Significant [Table Value of 'F' against df-310/2, 310/2 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance]

*At 0.05 level of Significance 3.03

*At 0.01 level of significance 4.68

Table 6 shows that the calculated *F-value* is less than the critical value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis failed to reject at both level of significance. Hence, there is a no significant mean difference based on the nature of course and devices used for learning with respect to their attitude towards the blended teaching-learning approach.

Figure 2: Dimension-wise attitude towards blended teaching-learning approach among Post Graduate level students

Source: Primary data (collected by researchers, 2023)

The eight dimensions of attitude towards the blended teaching-learning approach by post-graduate students depicted in Figure 2. In this first-dimensional graphical representation, students were dealing with the teaching-learning process. The majority of the students gave positive responses. In the second dimension, 120 students (out of 301 total) responded positively to learning activities. On the other hand, 130 students responded positively to psychological aspects regarding blended mode. Besides, many post-graduate students believed that a curriculum organized through blended mode is good. In the technology facilities dimension, 193 students responded positively to ‘agree’, while 75 students responded ‘neutral’, and 45 responded negatively with respect to technological facilities. In the fifth dimension, most students positively responded to the teacher’s efficiency. After that, the graphical representation reflects a critical aspect of the learner’s performance that most students struggle with the conceptual clarity of their respective courses. In another area, the majority of students were satisfied with the evaluation process in the blended teaching-learning process. Therefore, it was seen that most students supported the blended teaching-learning approach.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study revealed that most students (68.89%) scored between 56.038 and 66.019 indicating a moderate attitude towards the blended teaching-learning approach among post-graduate level students and the findings should be correlated with earlier study by Mahato et al (2021). It also found that most students were satisfied with the blended teaching-learning approach. Besides this, it is also revealed

that there is no significant difference in the attitudes based on gender (0.101, $p > 0.05$) which can be validated by the findings of Tongpoon-Patanasorn and White, (2020) residence (0.568, $p > 0.05$) which can be relevant to the previous study findings done by Jnr, (2022), family type (1.058, $p > 0.05$), semester at university (1.302, $p > 0.05$), nature of course (1.531, $p > 0.05$), nature of internet access (0.343, $p > 0.05$), devices used for learning (0.043, $p > 0.05$), Their experience of using the blended mode may be related to those of another study conducted by Hapuarachchi (2016). It is reasonable to conclude that attitudes regarding teaching-learning among PG students are similar. Besides, the study also revealed that majority of postgraduate students were satisfied with the dimensional aspects of blended teaching-learning approach which can be correlated with the previous work like Lim and Morris (2009), Sieweng and Muuk (2015). Therefore, it was clear that most students support the blended teaching-learning approach.

According to the findings, students believed that providing the course in a blended style made it easier to follow and boosted their learning. The online material was well-illustrated and simple to comprehend. The online activities boosted engagement and were well structured regarding goals and duration. It is critical that the course's intended learning objectives align with the online activities in order to ensure that the two elements are linked. Every course should be introduced in blended mode. Blended learning necessitates a deliberate approach to instructional design such that the program is blended in design, not merely in delivery.

Limitations and Future Research

In this study, the investigators selected 313 students to postgraduate level students at Uttar Dinajpur district of W.B., India. The study was restricted to enrolled samples of PG 1st and 3rd semester students. Also, the investigators only used the descriptive survey method for data collection and analyzed the data accordingly.

In order to achieve better content validity, future research may consider using additional items and dimensions. Also, further study can be carried out on challenges regarding blended teaching-learning in secondary-level students from different parts of the country. Also, future studies could include more universities and larger samples from different areas.

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